

A Systematic Review of Type 1 Diabetes Among Persons Experiencing Homelessness

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Abstract

Background: Type 1 Diabetes (T1D) requires stable insulin access, refrigeration, and consistent nutrition; conditions often unattainable for unhoused individuals. Standard clinical protocols frequently overlook these factors, and existing literature rarely disaggregates T1D from Type 2 Diabetes (T2D).

Objective: This systematic review (k=10) examines T1D management, clinical outcomes, and structural barriers among unhoused populations to identify evidence-based strategies for improving care.

Methods: Following PRISMA 2020 guidelines, seven databases were searched for studies reporting T1D outcomes and public health models. Data were synthesized using thematic narrative analysis.

Results: Homelessness is associated with poorer glycemic control and elevated emergency room utilization due to a lack of insulin refrigeration and food insecurity. Hospitalization, DKA, and macrovascular complication rates were found to be elevated in the unhoused population. Evidence indicates that supportive housing significantly improves process-of-care metrics and reduces emergency department visits. Heterogeneity was substantial, and few studies disaggregated between T1D and T2D.

Conclusion: Homelessness transforms T1D into an acute crisis rather than a chronic routine. Clinical practice must shift toward low-barrier, accessible models. Supportive housing is a foundational intervention for stabilizing endocrine outcomes.

Keywords: diabetes, T1D, homelessness, unhoused

1. Introduction

1.1 Rationale

Current literature on T1D among unhoused individuals is limited and often does not distinguish between T2D and T1D. To conceptualize and address the various contexts that affect physical and behavioral health needs, we need to examine current systems that impact the unhoused community [\[11\]](#).

Examining the connections and interactions between an unhoused person's immediate environment allows providers to see the links that directly influence the individual's physical and mental health development. This helps identify key determinants that influence health outcomes in these populations.

Nevertheless, this systematic review addresses the data gap and aims to strengthen the findings to promote agency among the unhoused population. This synthesis aims to identify overarching patterns across systems, such as structural demands that subsequently influence insulin-dependent diabetes [\[10\]](#).

1.2 Objectives

The objectives of this article are to systematically review and synthesize the literature on T1D among unhoused populations, focusing on management, outcomes, interventions, prevalence, patient experiences, and research gaps. This review aims to identify major clinical and structural barriers that prevent necessary management of T1D in the context of unstable housing. A central objective is to evaluate the translational potential of the literature; specifically, how identified structural and clinical barriers can inform real-world endocrinology practice and healthcare delivery adaptations for unhoused populations living with T1D.

2. Methods

2.1 Search Strategy

A comprehensive literature search was conducted in accordance with PRISMA 2020 guidelines. Seven electronic databases were searched: PubMed, PsycINFO, Google Scholar, SFSU OneSearch, Directory of Open Access Journals, OpenGrey, and Bielefeld. Searches were limited to studies published in English, with no restrictions on publication date. Search strategies incorporated both controlled vocabulary and free text keywords related to T1D and homelessness, combined using Boolean operators. Additional search strings were utilized to capture related themes, including: Outcomes, Management, Treatment, Glycemic Control, Barriers to Care, Healthcare Access, Mental Health, and Research Gaps. The PRISMA 2020 checklist is provided as a supplementary file.

Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion and Exclusion criteria are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Eligibility Criteria for Studies

	<i>Inclusion Criteria</i>	<i>Exclusion Criteria</i>
<i>Population</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants explicitly diagnosed with Type 1 Diabetes. • Address management, access-to-care, adherence, glycemic control, health outcomes, or interventions related to T1D • Subjects are unhoused individuals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Studies exclusively focused on Type 2 Diabetes. • Studies that do not clearly identify housing status within the population.
<i>Exposure/ Intervention & Outcomes</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Report on varying aspects of T1D in homeless populations, including but not limited to: Management, Outcomes, Intervention, Prevalence, Patient experiences, and Barriers to care 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Studies that lack clear relevance to T1D management, outcomes, interventions, prevalence, patient experiences, or barriers to care in the unhoused population. • Studies that provide no measurable outcomes or descriptive information relevant to type 1 diabetes among the unhoused.
<i>Study Design</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observational studies (e.g., cross-sectional, cohort, case-control studies). • Qualitative or mixed-method studies exploring experiences, challenges, and patient perspectives. • Interventional studies providing relevant outcome data specific to type 1 diabetes among homeless populations. • Other peer-reviewed studies reporting on type 1 diabetic management, outcomes, interventions, prevalence, patient experiences, or barriers to care 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Editorials, commentaries, opinion articles. • Conference abstracts or proceedings lacking detailed methodology or sufficient outcome data. • Reviews or meta-analyses (May be consulted for background information only.)

<i>Inclusion Criteria</i>	<i>Exclusion Criteria</i>
<p><i>Other Criteria</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Written in English. • No publication date restrictions. • Studies must be available in full text and provide sufficient data for extraction. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Studies assessed as having a high risk of bias or insufficient methodological rigor, as determined using standardized quality assessment tools applied to the appropriate study design (e.g., the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale or the Cochrane Risk of Bias Tool).

** This table summarizes the inclusion and exclusion criteria in the studies selected for this review. Studies were evaluated based on population characteristics, exposure/intervention and outcomes, study design, and other criteria.*

2.2 Study Selection and Data Extraction

Titles and abstracts were independently screened by at least three reviewers, followed by full-text review of eligible studies. Discrepancies were resolved by three consensus. Data were extracted using standardized forms that included study design, population characteristics, definitions of homelessness, and demographic details of participants. Studies were screened and selected if they met the inclusion criteria. T1D prevalence, outcomes, and barriers to care were extracted. Methodological characteristics and risk-of-bias assessments were also reviewed.

Table 2: Data Extraction Types

<i>Category</i>	<i>Data Extracted *</i>
<i>Study Characteristics</i>	Author(s), year of publication, study location, research design, methodology, sample size, and links/URLs to access the study.
<i>Population Characteristics</i>	Participants' demographics, definition of homelessness, and population classifications.

Type 1 Diabetes outcomes

T1D management, outcomes, interventions, prevalence, patient experiences, and research gap

Secondary Review Data

All studies underwent additional review and re-examination to ensure completeness and accuracy.

** Includes methodology for extractions, including what values were extracted.*

2.3 Risk of Bias and Certainty of Evidence

Study quality and risk of bias were assessed to support the interpretation of findings within a narrative synthesis. Longitudinal and population-based cohort studies were assessed using the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) and classified as high (7-9 stars), moderate (4-6 stars), or low quality/high risk of bias (0-3 stars). Cross-sectional, mixed-methods, and case-based studies were assessed using the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) critical appraisal tools. Both tools evaluate the appropriateness of the study design, methodological rigor, and reporting transparency. Certainty of evidence was described qualitatively.

Reporting bias was evaluated qualitatively as a protocol-based step, which identified selective reporting and the systematic lack of publications on T1D outcomes among unhoused populations. A quantitative pooling approach was also considered but not performed due to heterogeneity across study designs, definitions of outcomes, and the inclusion of single case reports, which limited comparability across studies. Nondisaggregated studies were ultimately included in the review in the context of a subgroup analysis in order to increase the quantity of included data. Consequently, a narrative synthesis was conducted in accordance with PRISMA 2020 guidelines and Cochrane Handbook guidelines. Thematic analysis was applied to identify recurring patterns in T1D management, outcomes, and barriers to care. Findings from

risk-of-bias assessments were integrated into the interpretation to contextualize the evidence base's strengths and limitations.

3. Results

3.1 Study Selection

Figure 1 illustrates the systematic selection and screening process of studies included in the review.

Fig 1. PRISMA flow chart. Created according to PRISMA2020 guidelines, using the SHINY flow diagram creation tool.

3.2 Risk of Bias in Studies

Methodological quality across the 10 studies demonstrated substantial heterogeneity. 2 studies were classified as high-quality (NOS: 8/9; JBI 7/8), utilizing representative samples and multivariable models to control for confounding variables. 6 studies demonstrated a moderate risk of bias due to limited follow-up procedures or potential misclassification of unhoused individuals. The remaining 2 studies were identified as high risk because they were both case studies that provided insights into lived experiences and lacked structured outcome measures or defined strategies.

3.3 Results of Synthesis

Table 3: Titles of the 10 studies used to determine Type 1 Diabetes among the unhoused population

<i>Study (Author, Year)</i>	<i>Country</i>	<i>Study Design</i>	<i>Sample size (n)</i>	<i>Definition/ Diagnosis Criteria used</i>	<i>Prevalence of T1D as Reported in each Study (%)</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Barriers Identified</i>	<i>Health Care Access</i>	<i>Interventions</i>	<i>Outcomes</i>	<i>Risk of Bias</i>
Oehring et al., 2025	UK	Cross-sectional and Mixed-methods	104	Survey of health professionals & volunteers	20% Median Perceived T1D	Diabetes clinicians , Inclusion health/ unhoused staff & VCSE providers	Drug use, transportation issues, and lack of education for providers	Hospital/ ED, Public health clinics	Outreach clinics mandate of homelessness flags in e-records	DKA, vision loss, limb amputation, dental issues	5/8 (JBI)
Hwang & Bugeja, 2000	CAN	Cross-Sectional	50	Self-reported diabetes	14%	Homeless adults	Storage & monitoring issues	Follow-up p/edu/med	Rec edu/ support	Self-care issues & ED use	5/8 (JBI)
Rasul et al., 2022	USA	Case Study	1	T1DM, 650 mg/dL	100% Single Case	Homeless adult male	Low Insulin Access	ED & Outreach	Insulin & Referral	Hosp Adm. & Toe Amput.	7/8 (JBI)
Colley et al., 2024	UK	Narrative/case vignette	1	Clinically and contextually	100% Single Case	Homeless adult male	Dietary barriers, barriers to healthcare access.	Limited access	Multidisciplinary support	Coordinated care	1/9
Scott et al., 2025	CAN	Mixed methods	40	Canadian policy def.	22.5%	Homeless adults	Healthcare access/limited care	On-site screening	Point-of-care screening	Increased screening	5/8 (JBI)
Arnaud et al., 2009	FRA	Cross-sectional	488	Shelter-based	0.02% out of diabetics & non-diabetics	Shelter residents	Irregular follow-up	Fragmented care	Rec. Foot care & screening	Not to discourage insulin due to low risk. Retinopathy & podiatry checkups.	6/8 (JBI)
Randall et al., 2011			164	Hospital patients	NR	Homeless adults & those with history of homelessness	Insulin noncompliance &	Uninsured	Rec Education & tailored care	Recurrent DKA	4/8 (JBI)
Sakai-Bizmark et al., 2020	USA	Longitudinal	11, 202	Medical Recs; Hospital-based homelessness	3.45% T1D in 643 homeless minors	Homeless v. Nonhomeless minors with diabetes	Unstable housing &h Hospitalizations	Hospital/ ED	Unspecified/none used	Hospitalization/ED/DKA/mortality/cost	8/9 (NOS)
Grewal et al., 2021	CAN	Mixed-methods	128	Self-reported diabetes and homelessness	3 (9.4) T1D or other	Homeless w/diabetes	Lack of food & housing	Navigati on & relationship gaps.	None	Disconnecti on between patients and food access.	5/8 (JBI)
Sharan et al., 2023	CAN	Cohort	~1.1M	Validated admin homelessness	2.4% T1D	Homeless v. nonhomeless	Suboptimal Glycemia & lack of medical access	Hospital	Rec. Screening & Social Support	Higher Diabetes rates in Homelessnes s	5/9 (NOS)

*Descriptions in the Results of Individual Studies are abbreviated for space. Complete descriptions are provided in the manuscript text.

Characteristics and key findings of the included studies are summarized in Table 3. Due to the substantial variation in study design and population size, a narrative synthesis was integrated, using thematic analysis to identify recurring patterns of clinical significance. The following sections: *Structural Barriers to Diabetes Management*, *Health Outcomes and Emergency Care Utilization*, and *Interventions and Care Models* summarize aggregated data on diabetes without indicating the prevalence or unique characteristics of T1D. *Type 1 Diabetes Prevalence and Outcomes* assesses the comparative prevalence of T1D in homeless versus general populations to highlight the risk associated with housing instability.

3.4 Structural Barriers to Diabetes Management

Disaggregated evidence identified substantial barriers to insulin-dependent management among unhoused individuals with T1D, including disrupted insulin storage, limited access to glucose monitoring supplies, irregular nutrition, lack of transportation to appointments, and difficulty scheduling appointments [1, 6, 10]. These systemic barriers reflect clinically relevant constraints that interfere with routine disease control and continuous care.

Findings from mixed T1D/T2D populations similarly described care access disruptions, impaired self-management capacity, and logistical service delivery barriers across outreach, shelter, and clinical settings, with associated impacts on glycemic stability, complication burden, and continuity of care [3, 4, 5, 6]. The instability of homelessness is characterized by a lack of private storage for medications and an absence of environmental control. Consequently, unhoused individuals are often forced to prioritize immediate survival as a trade-off for long-term disease management [8].

Evidence Specific to Type 1 Diabetes Management

Evidence directly addressing T1D management among unhoused individuals reports the consistent vulnerability associated with complete insulin dependence. Unhoused individuals with T1D frequently reported the inability to safely store insulin due to a lack of refrigeration and limited access to glucose monitoring [6]. These barriers are compounded by irregular meal timing, fear of theft, and unstable living conditions, which often complicate insulin dosing and daily management [6, 8]. One article detailed a case report of a male who had his glucose monitoring equipment stolen, missed follow-up care, and experienced difficulty storing insulin [1]. To address the patient's history of missed appointments and equipment loss, the clinical team utilized the hospitalization period to establish a long-term management strategy. Some strategies implemented included modifying their dispensing schedules and coordinating refills to reduce their supply gaps. Other strategies offered remote diabetes support and mobile device-based appointment reminders to ensure continuity of care. Utilizing this model of care prevented future follow-up failures while resolving insulin storage challenges [1]. This case highlights how unstable housing disrupts routine T1D management and requires life-saving adaptive care strategies.

Management Evidence From Mixed T1D/T2D Populations

Evidence from mixed T1D/T2D populations highlights systemic barriers to diabetes management among individuals experiencing homelessness. In survey data from Toronto, Canada, 72% of respondents indicated that they had difficulties adhering to medication, follow-up care, and diabetes management due to their unstable environment [6]. Similarly, preliminary data from Miami Street Medicine documented inconsistencies in glucose

monitoring, further highlighting the challenges of sustaining routine blood glucose monitoring outside a clinical setting [3].

In order to remedy the negative effects homelessness has on diabetes, a Calgary-based point-of-care screening program provided on-site glucose monitoring, foot care, and specialist referrals. However, fewer than half of the patients attended specialist appointments outside the program. Unhoused individuals often experience pervasive structural barriers that force them to prioritize securing shelter and safety over medical appointments, consequently, undermining diabetes management and glycemic control [5].

Common material barriers cited were inflexible appointment times and financial constraints. Many healthcare providers also reported they received insufficient training on unhoused individuals with diabetes, had limited access to resources for patients, struggled with complex patient needs, and had difficulties procuring diabetes screenings and contacting patients for follow-ups [10].

3.5 Health Outcomes

Disaggregated evidence demonstrated substantial clinical outcome disparities among unhoused individuals with T1D, including mortality, markedly elevated hospitalization and emergency department utilization, longer lengths of stay, and disproportionate pediatric admission rates relative to housed peers [4]. Mixed T1D/T2D findings document a higher risk of glycemic emergencies, macrovascular complications, infections, and severe diabetes sequelae.

Evidence Specific to Type 1 Diabetes Outcomes

While studies examining T1D among unhoused individuals are limited, one retrospective analysis provided clear insights into T1D-specific outcomes. Homeless minors experience a

substantially higher hospitalization rate compared to their non-homeless peers (2.96 vs 0.34 per 1,000; $P < 0.01$). This disparity is further reflected in readmission data, where homeless T1D patients demonstrated a disproportionate rate of return to acute care (20.4% vs. 14.1%, $P < 0.01$) and extended lengths of stay (IRR 1.20, $P < 0.01$), compared to the non-homeless population. Notably, these elevated risks persisted even when compared to non-homeless patients' income quartile, indicating that unstable housing contributes to adverse clinical outcomes in T1D [4].

A case study of an unsheltered male with a history of T1D illustrates the severity and dangers of metabolic decompensation in cases of unstable insulin access. This patient presented a point-of-care glucose measurement of 650 mg/dL, leading to severe complications that included DKA and multiple toe amputations. After receiving 10 units of insulin, the patient was immediately escorted to the ED for further treatment. Upon arrival, the individual was admitted to the general medicine floor for DKA management and wound care. The patient's hospital course was complicated by multiple infections related to underlying acute conditions, ultimately necessitating amputation of the right second and third toes [3].

Evidence From Mixed T1D/T2D Populations Outcomes

Findings from large mixed-diabetes cohorts evaluate outcomes using combined, non-disaggregated samples in which T1D and T2D are analyzed together. In a population-based cohort study with 1,076,437 individuals, this non-disaggregated diabetes sample demonstrated that individuals experiencing homelessness ($n = 5,219$) had worse clinical outcomes. Rates of macrovascular complications were higher among the unhoused group (RR 1.85, 95% CI 1.64–2.07), as were rates of hospitalization for glycemic emergencies (RR 5.64, 95% CI 4.07–7.81) and skin or soft-tissue infections (RR 3.78, 95% CI 3.31–4.32). The rate of

macrovascular complications among individuals with a history of homelessness was 37.3 per 1,000 person-years, compared with 72.4 per 1,000 person-years among nonhomeless controls (RR 1.85, 95% CI 1.64-2.07) [2].

A national survey of 104 frontline UK professionals, including specialist nurses, physicians, and dietitians, revealed a systemic failure in care, with 57% rating diabetes outcomes for people experiencing homelessness as "poor" or "very poor". 66% of respondents reported that complications from diabetes occurred more frequently in unhoused individuals. Leg and lower limb amputations were highlighted as being more prevalent in unhoused individuals than in the general population, as were vision loss, cardiovascular complications, and dental problems. Approximately 25% of respondents reported more frequent complications, including neuropathic pain, foot infections, and DKA [10].

While diabetes type was not specified, findings from the Miami Street Medicine suggest that homelessness is a significant risk factor for uncontrolled DM. Preliminary data from the Miami Street Medicine indicate that among 29 patients tested for blood glucose, 52% (N=15) met the criteria for hyperglycemia (blood glucose > 140 mg/dL) [3]. Moreover, a cross-sectional study of homeless shelters in Paris found that 6.1% had known diabetes with a disproportionately high frequency of major complications such as retinopathy, amputations, and elevated podiatric risk [7]. Although not disaggregated by diabetes type, these reports demonstrate the clinical severity that is often associated with unmanaged diabetes in unhoused settings.

3.6 Type 1 Diabetes Prevalence

The accurate determination of T1D prevalence among homeless individuals is constrained by a significant lack of large studies. Despite the logistical challenges, the findings

suggest that T1D prevalence rates are elevated in the unhoused population. For instance, a cross-sectional study conducted in a Toronto shelter found that 14% (7 out of 50) of homeless adults with diabetes had T1D [6].

A cross-sectional, mixed-methods study surveyed 104 frontline diabetes specialists, emergency care physicians, and public health volunteers across four domains of UK healthcare. Across all surveyed clinicians, 34.5% of unhoused people with diabetes were estimated to have T1D, while 65.5% were estimated to have T2D. This indicates that T1D is perceived to be substantially more prevalent among unhoused populations in the UK compared to the general UK population, with T1D accounting for roughly 8% of diabetics. According to the 104 respondents, in the UK, unhoused individuals are 4.3x more likely to have T1D. It was also found that 80% of homeless patients across clinics were reported to need insulin therapy, suggesting that a majority of unhoused people in the UK either have T1D or advanced insulin-dependent T2D [10].

Further, a Canadian population-based cohort study revealed a T1D prevalence of 2.4% among people with a history of homelessness and diabetes, compared with 2.1% in the non-homeless control group [2].

3.7 Interventions

Across the literature, interventions targeting diabetes care among unhoused populations demonstrate adapted healthcare delivery into integrated medical behavioral care, street medicine outreach, and shelter-embedded services. These strategies prioritize insulin access, monitoring, wound management, and care continuity in nontraditional settings [1,3,7].

In studies involving mixed T1D and T2D cohorts, street medicine and medical outreach are primary drivers for treatment. These interventions facilitate insulin access, glucose monitoring, and hospital referrals by operating directly within shelters or through street-level outreach [3]. Moreover, integrating clinic-based screenings with social services helps reduce the fragmentation of care often seen in traditional clinic-based models [1,7].

The Housing-First model represents the most significant intervention for improving clinical utilization. Establishing housing stability addresses the root causes of healthcare fragmentation that studies continue to demonstrate among unsheltered individuals [1,7,9]. Observational and Population-based studies report reductions in emergency department visits, hospital admissions, and preventable complications following housing placement [2,4,5]. As is evident, administrative data confirms that housing stability provides the necessary foundation for care [10].

4. Discussion

Summary of Evidence

This systematic review synthesizes limited but relevant evidence on T1D among individuals experiencing homelessness, demonstrating that structural barriers shift management from routine outpatient care to acute risk. Effective glycemic control depends on reliable insulin access, refrigeration, nutrition, and environmental stability; conditions frequently absent in homelessness, contributing to consistently poorer metabolic outcomes. The review also highlights a critical literature gap: many diabetes-homelessness studies fail to distinguish between T1D and T2D, limiting insulin-specific clinical guidance.

Across studies, poor glycemic control was consistently observed, with elevated HbA1c levels and inadequate control reported in up to 44% of participants. Insulin cold-chain failure in environments outside of the 36-86 degrees Fahrenheit range, food insecurity, and underdosing to avoid hypoglycemia were recurrent barriers, compounded by logistical obstacles to follow-up care. However, some diabetes experts believe that hypoglycemia is no longer as significant a concern with modern medications. According to a 2006 paper, homeless diabetics should be given normal dosages of insulin and take them at regular intervals [6]. Diabetes experts should be briefed on proper dosing and medication management for individuals facing homelessness, and can utilize existing tools to characterize risk factors and diabetes severity specific to unhoused populations. For instance, the SAFER model includes screening protocols for HbA1C, feet, eyes, and renal function, and includes an easy-to-read flowchart detailing how to coordinate care based on measurements [12]. These factors shift care toward emergency and acute services, with higher ED visits, hospitalizations, DKA, hypoglycemia, and severe complications. Lower DKA rates in some pediatric cohorts likely reflect earlier admission or survivorship bias rather than improved control.

Interventional findings underscore the centrality of housing stability to improving outcomes. Supportive housing and integrated care models were associated with improved monitoring, medication access, and reduced acute utilization, with complementary benefits from street medicine and harm-reduction programs. However, interpretation remains constrained by misclassification of diabetes type, which obscures insulin-dependent risk patterns and limits precision in estimating prevalence, complications, and care needs specific to T1D.

4.1 Strengths

A major strength of this systematic review is its rigorous and transparent methodology, adhering to PRISMA 2020 guidelines across study identification, screening, and synthesis. Predefined eligibility criteria, independent screening by three reviewers, and standardized data extraction enhanced reproducibility while minimizing bias. Formal risk-of-bias assessments, including the NOS for cohort studies and JBI tools for cross-sectional and mixed-methods designs, further strengthened data quality appraisal.

Another strength of this review is its effort to disaggregate T1D from the broader diabetes literature, which is predominantly focused on T2D. Many health services studies do not distinguish diabetes type, limiting interpretability for insulin-dependent populations [2,4,5]. By prioritizing studies identifying T1D or insulin dependence, this synthesis addresses a critical evidence gap and enables more precise interpretation of outcomes specific to T1D, including insulin access disruptions, DKA, infection risk, and acute care utilization [2,7].

This review also integrates findings across diverse study designs and health system contexts, including population-based cohorts, clinical case reports, mixed-methods outreach evaluations, and professional surveys [3,4,6,10].

Despite methodological variation, studies consistently reported similar themes, potentially offsetting heterogeneity. The presence of negative results, such as lower rates of DKA among minors with diabetes, suggests publication bias may be lower than originally suspected.

4.2 Limitations

Many large cohort and cross-sectional studies failed to distinguish between T1D and T2D, potentially leading to inaccurate conclusions about T1D. Because T1D requires uninterrupted exogenous insulin for survival, aggregating diabetes subtypes obscures risks unique to insulin-dependent individuals and prevents attribution of outcomes to insulin interruption rather than T2D-associated metabolic dysregulation. In unhoused populations, DKA reflects structural failures in insulin access, storage, and continuity of care.

The certainty of evidence is further weakened by methodological limitations and inconsistent adjustment for key confounders, including mental illness, substance use, and other comorbidities. Material barriers also reduce the quality of care and follow-up appointments, including a lack of a permanent address, transportation, and identification [1,2]. These factors are highly prevalent among unhoused populations and are independently associated with adverse diabetes outcomes.

Across studies, marked heterogeneity in health outcome measures, objectives, and housing classifications precluded meta-analytic pooling, leading to a study design that included thematic analysis and qualitative approaches. It was found that 80% of studies were rated moderate-to-high risk of bias, which may have led to the wide variation in study quality and incomplete adjustment for confounders, further reducing confidence in pooled conclusions.

4.4 Implications

This systematic review emphasizes the implications for health care systems, practitioners, and advocates for individuals with T1D who experience homelessness. A fundamental lack of

resources drives the poor health outcomes experienced by this population. Unstable insulin storage and difficulty maintaining continuity of care are some of the most frequently cited barriers. Limited knowledge of specific barriers further compounds the challenges of caring for this transient population.

Clinical practice must therefore shift toward providing referrals to social services for housing to properly store medical supplies, and for transportation to appointments. Psychosocial and mental health factors must not be overlooked[8]. Low-barrier care, such as shelter-based or outreach clinics, should incorporate routine and nonjudgmental screening for insulin misuse. They should also record mistrust of providers and supply theft to facilitate the prevention of acute and emergent outcomes [3,5,8].

Practical recommendations for clinicians include simplifying insulin regimens where appropriate, prioritizing basal insulin during food insecurity, applying harm-reduction dosing strategies when meals are unpredictable, and coordinating access to safe insulin storage and sharps disposal pathways [1,6,10]. From a systems and documentation perspective, clinicians and researchers should recognize that administrative coding alone is insufficient to characterize T1D risk among unhoused populations. Standardized documentation of housing status, diabetes type/insulin dependence, and reliable contact pathways may improve follow-up planning and surveillance of T1D outcomes [10].

5. Conclusion

Homelessness imposes profound structural and logistical barriers that interfere with T1D management, increasing the risk of adverse events and preventing timely screening and care.

Diabetes self-management is frequently compromised by inadequate insulin refrigeration, while pervasive food insecurity disrupts glycemic stability and heightens hypoglycemia risk, rendering standard care incompatible with the instability of homelessness. Consequently, unhoused individuals living with T1D experience markedly poorer health outcomes, including higher rates of acute complications such as DKA and substantially elevated hospitalization and emergency department utilization compared to housed populations. Targeted interventions tailored to the needs of unhoused individuals with T1D are essential towards improving health outcomes. Strategies must account for barriers to insulin storage and consistent nutrition. Supportive housing plays a critical role in stabilizing environmental conditions, enabling more effective disease management, and reducing avoidable hospitalizations.

Declarations

6.1 Ethics

This study is a systematic analysis of aggregated prevalence data from peer-reviewed studies on diabetes among individuals experiencing homelessness. All included studies were assumed to have obtained appropriate institutional ethical approval and informed consent at the time of their original data collection. No new informed consent was required, as no individual-level or identifiable data were accessed. Accordingly, this study did not constitute human subjects research and was exempt from institutional review board review.

6.2 Funding and Conflicts of Interest

The authors have no known conflicts of interest in the outcomes of this study, nor any incentive to represent findings in a biased manner. As a systematic review, the project did not require direct funding.

6.3 Declaration of Generative AI Usage

During the preparation of this work, the authors used NotebookLM and Grammarly to improve grammatical, spelling, and organizational clarity. After using this service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

6.4 Acknowledgments

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7. Glossary

T1D (Type 1 Diabetes): A chronic autoimmune disease characterized by insulin dependence.

T2D (Type 2 Diabetes): A metabolic disorder characterized by insulin resistance and relative insulin deficiency, often managed with lifestyle changes and medications.

HbA1c (Hemoglobin A1c): A laboratory measure reflecting average blood glucose levels over the prior 2–3 months.

DKA (Diabetic Ketoacidosis): A life-threatening emergency caused by severe insulin deficiency leading to hyperglycemia, ketone production, and metabolic acidosis.

Hyperglycemia: Abnormally high blood glucose levels; a blood glucose level above 140 mg/dL.

Hypoglycemia: Dangerously low blood glucose levels; a blood glucose level below 70mg/dL.

Macrovascular Complications: Chronic complications affecting large blood vessels, such as myocardial infarction or stroke.

Microvascular Complications: Chronic complications affecting small blood vessels, including retinopathy (eyes), nephropathy (kidneys), and neuropathy (nerves).

Cold-Chain Failure: The disruption of the temperature-controlled supply chain required to keep insulin effective.

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List of Figure Captions

Fig 1. PRISMA flow chart. Created according to PRISMA2020 guidelines, using the SHINY flow diagram creation tool.